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Further intensification of push-pull for better livelihoods of smallholder farmers.

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Push-pull technology is one of the intensification practices that has been used to increase yield and income in smallholder cereal-based production systems by controlling insect pests (fall armyworm and stemborer) and the parasitic striga weed, while improving soil health and providing fodder for crop-livestock integration. The technology is however restricted to maize and traditional cereals, and application is limited to the scale of fields. Harnessing the full potential of push-pull requires further intensification of the technology. An on-going research in Western Kenya seeks to expand the scope and applicability of push-pull in smallholder farming systems. Ten focus group discussions with 91 participants drawn from 10 villages in three counties (Kisumu, Siaya and Vihiga), and key informant interviews with 25 participants from the same region were used to identify sustainable intensification practices that farmers want integrated in push-pull systems. Respondents were aware of, and mentioned mixed farming, intercropping, crop rotation, push-pull system, use of fertilizers and organic manure, good agronomic practices, agroforestry and conservation agriculture as the practices they adopt to increase crop yields without expanding the area under cultivation. Similar sustainable intensification practices were mentioned across counties, implying that environmental context played minimal or no influence on these practices. Respondents rated mixed farming, intercropping and crop rotation as the most widely practiced in the region. They prefer to intensify push-pull with options that would increase productivity, boost income and provide firewood and fodder. However, broader challenges to uptake of technologies in the region (e.g. shortage of land due to high population, dearth of information on some of the approaches, aggravated by lack of skills and shortage of extension agents, broader cultural issues of land ownership and land use that prejudice against women and youth, high costs of inputs, and limited access to market) affect adoption of push-pull.

Keywords: Intercropping, desmodium, cereals, focus group discussion, key informant interviews